

**ERASMUS - A BRIGHT REPRESENTATIVE OF THE EUROPEAN
RENAISSANCE**

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Annotation:

The scientific article provides information about the life and creative activity of Erasmus, one of the famous representatives of the Renaissance.

Key words:

Renaissance, Germany, humanism, Thomas More, Oxford, Martin Luther

Science and culture developed at a high level during the Renaissance in Europe. During this period, many innovations were made in science and other fields. New examples of creativity have appeared. Many artists and writers lived in this period. One of the unique artists of this period was Erasmus

Erasmus has a special place in the history of German humanism. He was born on October 28, 1469. But some sources say that he was born in 1466 or 1467. He got the nickname Rotterdamsky because he was born near Rotterdam. Erasmus mainly studies classical languages at school. He travels to several European cities in search of work. From 1486 to 1492, he lived in the monastery of Augustine monks, where he received the title. Erasmus devoted his free time to learning, reading books, learning Latin and ancient Greek languages, learning the basics of public speaking. He is preparing for the position of secretary of the bishop of one of the cities of France. Later, on a trip to London, he met Thomas More, John Fisher and John Colet. In addition, he met and talked with the King of Great Britain, Henry VIII. He organized trips to Holland, Great Britain, France and Italy.

He continuously propagated this culture in his works. Erasmus laughed at obscurantism in his numerous works and made a worthy contribution to the widespread development of humanistic views. Erasmus evaluated the reality of his contemporary from the position of a humanistic enlightened person, and looked at the fate of the oppressed people with pity. In 1500, Erasmus published a collection of proverbs and proverbs taken from the works of ancient writers in Latin, later this book was republished several times with additions. He is recognized as a connoisseur of works of ancient authors. He establishes friendly relations with many European humanists. His first books were published in Paris.

He establishes relations with Thomas More by letter. In 1506, he went to Italy, the cradle of European humanism, and wanted to get acquainted with the archives of Italian libraries and study unknown manuscripts in ancient Greek and Latin languages. He had the opportunity to stay in Italy and expand the science of piety. He received his Doctor of Theology degree in Turin, Italy. It was possible for him to occupy a profitable and for that time proud church career. But Erasmus needed In 1509, Erasmus went to England. Along the way, he wrote the work "The Honorable Word of Ignorance", which brought him world fame. He demonstrates his philological and theological abilities while preparing a Greek critical text of the Gospel. In addition, he spent a lot of effort to interpret and prepare for publication the works of Catholic authors who lived in the early period of Christianity. Analyzing their work, Erasmus pointed out that the Catholic Church, which he was a contemporary of, lacked simplicity and sincerity and violated the "testaments of the church fathers". In this way, he was preparing the reformation. While living in England, Erasmus received an offer from Oxford in 1506, but he accepted the offer from Cambridge University, where he taught religion and Greek. In 1511, he was elected a professor at Cambridge.

From 1514 he lived mainly in Basel. All European humanists listened to his voice. His works were distributed in large circulation for that time. His works strengthened the critical attitude against scholasticism, fostered love for people,

knowledge and desire for freedom. But when the reformation movement started, Erasmus treated it very cautiously. In 1524, he wrote a treatise entitled "Discussion on the Freedom of the Will", in which he wrote about the right of a person to determine his own destiny, not to be a slave of divine forces.

In the debate with Martin Luther, as a humanist, he prefers critical thinking and understanding to blind faith. He entered the lives of the next generations with his two works "The Honorable Word of Ignorance" and the satire "Ordinary Dialogues". "The Honorable Word of Ignorance" is written in a humorous tone, while analyzing social phenomena, it tries to talk about ignorance and show that it has a great position in reality. With this, Erasmus exposes many of the ugliness of his time and laughs at them. In his works, he emphasizes the importance of the beginning of emotional cognition in human life. "If man was not at the disposal of the emotional element, he writes, the human race would not have continued, do you mean the same thing?" I thought so myself. None of you are idiots who disagree with me. If life is not given a pinch of ignorance, then there will be sadness, boredom, and suffering?" With this idea, Erasmus appears to us as a man of the Renaissance, a great life-loving Stoic, and a person who cannot bear to see asceticism. He loves life and wants to accept it as it is. As a great scientist of the Renaissance, he appreciates dedication to science, but does not support one-sided devotion. Erasm's bitter satire is not aimed at working people, he writes about working people in tones of sympathy.

Erasm, whose work "Words of Honor" was written with love for people and people, directs his anger at the enemies of intelligence, science and life. The popularity of his book and its role in the preparation of the Reformation can be explained by this. Erasmus' work "Adagia" was famous among his contemporaries. Some of these stories had detailed comments and acquired an openly journalistic character. For example, in one of the conversations, the eagle is described as a "bird" that carries poison, disrupts peace and tranquility, and is born for fighting

and robbery. He clearly shows how the hokims of his contemporaries destroy the peace of ordinary people who are dependent on him.

In 1518, the first edition of the book "Ordinary dialogues" written in the style of conversations by Erasmus was published. This book is made up of different conversations on life topics, people of different classes and ages, different professions and interests talk to each other. As a result, Germany and its morals are painted inside scenes. Erasmus wants to revive the reality of that time through conversations about the relationship between the master and the king, the medieval education system, and the worries of the priests about the pain of income. He also pays great attention to the theme of love and family in this work; writes about unfaithful women and men and defends a healthy and faithful family built on the basis of mutual respect and love. As always, Erasmus laughs at the monks, criticizes the dogmas of the church. In the book, the ideal of Erasmus is given through the interpretation of the image of Eusebius. The hero of the play has a wonderful house on the outskirts of the city, a garden and a garden, and the blessings of the garden and garden are at the disposal of the public, he says. The cradle of the garden is always open for widows and is guarded only at night. Let the orphans be happy, even if it is at their own expense. With this, he wants to prevent the poverty of people. Yevsevi has a wonderful library, and devotes his solitude to reading books and talking with friends. In this utopia, Erasmus' strengths and weaknesses are revealed. His weakness was his detachment from the struggles of the times, but his strong points were his desire for spiritual freedom, spiritual equality, and non-adjustment to the terrible reality. Although the characters in his works strive for solitude, the personal life of the writer was not completely secluded. The writer's life was full of continuous struggles, and Erasmus himself remained in the memory of mankind as a freedom fighter. He died on July 12, 1536.

In conclusion, his ideas and works became famous throughout Europe. Many of his works have been republished. Special attention was paid to the study of his

work and it is being studied to this day. He went down in history as one of the figures who left an indelible mark on the European Renaissance.

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